

THE ROLE OF TOURIST PERCEPTION AND MOTIVATION IN SHAPING SUSTAINABLE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Sustainable tourism is tourism that considers the future and that can contribute to the survival of the industry. Regrettably, sustainable tourism has not been fully integrated into society at the anticipated magnitude. This study was aimed to identify any factors that enable sustainable tourism development. The study employed a quantitative approach and used nonprobability sampling with a sample examination of as many as 200 respondents. The data was collected through online surveys using a Likert scale. This study applies to external and internal models completed using structural equation modeling 3.0. Based on the research results and analysis, it can be concluded that variables such as tourism perception, positive impact, experiential satisfaction, destination image, and motivation have a positive and significant influence on the sustainable tourism development attitude, and it is possible to conclude that all hypotheses are accepted. This research is expected to contribute to developing knowledge about how tourists can preserve natural resources and contribute to future tourism development, especially from the perception of tourists from different countries. Thus, this research provides valuable contributions in filling the gaps in knowledge about the real attitudes of tourists toward preserving and contributing to environmental sustainability to develop future tourism.

Keywords: Tourist Perception, Experiential Satisfaction, Motivation, Sustainable Tourism.

INTRODUCTION

The World Tourism Organization (WTO) explains that sustainable tourism is tourism that considers the future along with current economic, social, and environmental effects in responding to visitors' needs. The sustainability principle is based on some aspects of it, and the right balance should be built among the three aspects to ensure tourism's survival (Santos-Roldán et al., 2020a). Sustainable tourism is not just nature conservation or socially responsible behavior. The theory defines sustainable tourism as involving the dimensions of economic, social protection, and anger. In this context, the less-observed problem was social involvement (Streimikiene et al., 2021).

Tourism plays a role in social integrity in which activities can be considered as a limit for measuring social integration, as it provides the opportunity to realize correlations with cognition and other cultures and also organize culturally-related associations so that time can be economically and effectively spent (Cloquet et al., 2018). Cultural tourism is included in the tourism category and occurs when visitors can discover and study reservoirs or cultural attractions, both tangible and intangible, in an area to meet the tourism objectives of that area (Kalvet et al., 2020). Tourism is experiencing rapid

development on the European continent and also serves thousands of people, and it is included as a form of social integration that includes universal rights related to the tourism sector based on value requirements as the main criteria for tourism development in the social sector (Streimikiene et al., 2021).

Motivation is defined in various studies as a theoretical explanation of how something has been implemented (Elliot et al., 2006) and is related to behavior as a form of representation of the background of people's actions and needs. Motivation also has other meanings, from the way an individual behaves or expresses the causes when he or she repeats an action to the theory of socialization that states the characteristics of the association that will develop tourism to review funds and the effectiveness of its development. Meanwhile, indicators related to intrinsic motivation are a form of indicator to determine other support for the Sustainable Development Group (Meimand et al., 2017). Motivation is related to sustainably developed tourism in determining a destination (C. L. Chang et al., 2020), and also the experience gained is crucial to making motivation more satisfied and optimizing the loyalty of tourists when the profile or identity details of consumers include tourists who have a full commitment to sustainable environmental awareness (Liu et al., 2016).

Several studies have found a good relationship between the impact of attitudes against sustainable tourism and an insight into the positive impact (Hsieh et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2015). In the tourism context, motivation is defined as the important value associated with the behavioral intention of returning to a place from word of mouth and looking for another resort destination (Santos-Roldán et al., 2020).

A higher level fosters good behavior in the future like revisiting a destination (Castillo Canalejo & Jimber del Río, 2018). The relationship between attitudes and also motivation against sustainable development has been observed in some research (Huang & Liu, 2017). Analysis with motivation is used as an internal indicator to serve as a guide regarding individual attitudes and as an indicator of the psychological aspect to show someone how to correctly act so that their goals can be achieved as well as being a force to encourage someone to achieve their goals (Santos-Roldán et al., 2020).

The combination of expectations and needs is defined as a motivation that has an impact on tendencies in organizing a trip (Jeong et al., 2018); thus, insight into motivation can provide assistance for managers to organize services and facilities to meet customer needs, and there are various factors to do so (Albayrak & Caber, 2018). Attractions and exploration can make destinations appear stronger and more unique, and it is also used as a motivator to trigger comparisons between one destination and another (Ritchie & Crouch, 2003).

Tourists' views that are interpreted to have a positive influence on tourism should be urgently explored, and the reason for optimizing this value is that there are both negative and positive impacts on tourism from local communication (Lankford & Howard, 1994). Differences in views from residents can contribute insights into evaluations related to tourist destinations as a reference to urgently plan successful development in society (Ko

& Stewart, 2002). Images are the subject of a complex interpretation in terms of how people feel interested in an organization and in identifying image indicators, including images, locations, products, and services. To create the desired image, a company must focus on service quality, customer expectation, image, and customer satisfaction to maintain the sustainability of the company (Barusman, 2020).

Exploration satisfaction is a construct that can provide mediation of views and can also influence the quality of experience. Behavior and beliefs related to the reputation of an institution or company concerning satisfaction related to an experience can optimize the intention to behave positively toward visitors. The management of cultural heritage also needs to implement its principles to prioritize (Lee et al., 2007). Satisfying visitors by providing quality experiences or performances is shown to measure the views of tourists and also physical equipment with certain attractions that will ultimately have a positive impact on customer satisfaction (Chew & Jahari, 2014).

Krippendorf (1982) proved that a destination must review its perceptions from tourists, and when a tourist visits a destination, to compare perceptions with reality. In this way, perceptions can be used as a guide for evaluation in the tourism and marketing sectors, which are very fun. There are various studies related to perceptions in the tourism sector that suggest that tourism factors are very urgent to increase the positive impression of a business destination so that it can apply management principles referring to what is valued by tourists (Kong et al., 2015). Although tourism has increasingly been recognized as a practice in the business sector, academic research is also an integral part of particular relevance and development in terms of tourism that has always been based on preserving the environment and cultural authenticity as well as benefits for the tourism sector (Santos-Roldán et al., 2020). To analyze the impact of potential meaning creation and purpose exploration on the behavior response of tourists, this study assumes that human attitudes have a cause, which is the stimulation from the surrounding environment so that it can have an impact on behavioral and also cognitive aspects (Diener et al., 1999). Emotion is the paradigm from the demand aspect that assumes that destinations are the main suppliers of spatial tourism services with certain features that have high attractiveness so that they can improve the feelings of tourists (Cracolici & Nijkamp, 2009). Entertainment builds emotional cooperation between tourists, and offerings with characteristics that can give a good impression become powerful facilities to attract customers. The local community can complement tourism with experiences or explorations as well as existing natural resources so that it can connect the feelings and identity of the group to the community in the local area (Reitsamer & Brunner-Sperdin, 2017).

Tourist garbage is a common problem all over the world. In Thailand, the Khao Yai National Park near Bangkok is one of the most popular tourist destinations. However, the administrators and officials of Thailand have been overwhelmed by the unclean tourists who dump their garbage in vain and destroy the natural beauty while endangering the animals that live there (Mutiah, 2020). The number of tourists in Bali, Yogyakarta, and Lampung can be seen on the data of the Central Statistical Agency (BPS) and other

sources. The number of Nusantara tourists to Lampung in 2023 is 8.855.256 people; for Yogyakarta, the number of Nusantara tourist in 2023 is 6.599 people; and the numbers of foreign tourists shows a fairly significant increase, that is, as many as 3.883 people come in the beginning of the year. Bali data shows a fairly significant increase in the number of tourists, with 370,832 visits in March 2023 compared to 14,620 in March 2022. The diverse culture and high natural wealth of Indonesia is a very crucial element in the tourism sector where the environment includes 17,001 islands and 6,000 of them are uninhabited with a tropical climate. Indonesia also has the longest coastline after the European Union and Canada (Barusman, 2020). However, garbage production in tourist destinations increases as tourist visits increase. This high waste production not only destroys environmental order but also disrupts ecosystems and threatens biodiversity. Literature reviews about the STD (Sustainable Tourism Development) have mostly been in Asia (Kawuryan et al., 2022), but only a few have discussed Indonesia. Meanwhile, in Indonesia there are still many tourist sites that are not aware of the sustainability of tourism development. One example is Lampung, such as the island of Pahawang. According to a direct observation from the news, not only garbage from leaves and tree branches was found on the island of Pahawang but also a lot of plastic waste used for food and beverages discarded by visitors on the shore (Hariko, 2023). There has been damage to parts of the coral reef, which is an attraction on Pahawang Island. There have not been enough preventative efforts to maintain the beauty there. The world's visitor's visit are unlimited and visitors have a negative impact by damaging coral reefs. The problem is that there is no certain distance between the crowd of tourists and the visitor center as well as the point of attraction as something that attracts the interest of tourists there (Barusman, 2020).

The orientation of this research is to detail various indicators with certain probabilities and their impact on tourism in a sustainable manner, measuring the indicators by using several variables. Based on the provided background, this study focuses on the influence of tourist perception, positive impact, experiential satisfaction, and image on sustainable tourism development attitude, with motivation as a moderating variable. Based on the presented formulation of the problem, the purpose of this research is to: (1) find the factors that enable sustainable tourism development; and (2) determine whether the perceptions of tourists affect the intentions and attitudes in visiting tourist destinations

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Relationship between Tourist Perception and Positive Impact

Aware of the abandonment of tourism, many researchers oppose the exploration of correlations related to behavior and places from the perspective of tourists and the positive social impact they provide, including usefulness for society, the optimization of values, and times of pride and cultural associations (Qu et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2021). Meanwhile, negative impacts in general include crime and vandalism, prostitution, and alcohol abuse (Joo et al., 2019). Environmental psychology studies reveal the relationship that has a positive impact between us and the environment with its influence on mental

and physical spiritual effects (Ramkissoon, 2023). Based on the research here, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Tourists' views of tourism have a direct positive impact on attitudes to develop tourism sustainably.

Correlation of Experience Satisfaction and Tourist Views

In tourism, choose very high competence so that the main defender becomes a strategic key component of the business and vice versa if expectations cannot be met, then the tourist area will not be large (Kotler et al., 2017). According to Gnanapala (2015), the concept is very urgent with its impact on the influence of future purchases and also publicity and market share. Tourist satisfaction is the presence of emotional and cognitive feelings that are mainly based on expectations and also the image of the destination and feelings of values. The mechanism for determining the destination is based on the impact of attitudes and perceptions, and also motives and perception are defined as a mechanism (Wang et al., 2009). When rules and choices are determined by a person in manifesting his or her stimuli as a coherent description.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Tourist perceptions have a direct and positive influence on experience satisfaction in returning to tourist destinations.

The Relationship between Tourist Perception and Destination Image

Studies of the relationship between tourist perception and destination image have been carried out by several researchers. Some findings show that destination image has a positive influence on tourist satisfaction (Sitanggang & Pangestuti, 2020). In addition, the destination performed and the behavior of the tourism, so it is logical to link the risk concept (Setiawan, 2018). Other research findings show that the image of a tourist destination can affect tourist satisfaction as well as tourist loyalty (Sakti, 2018). Tourist perceptions of safety and risk significantly affect the image of the destination and the behavior of the tourist, so it is logical to link tourism to the concept of risk (Chew & Jahari, 2014). Thus, it can be concluded that destination images play an important role in influencing the perception and satisfaction of tourists. Thus, the following hypothesis is formulated:

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Tourist perceptions have a direct and positive influence on the image of the destination in affecting tourist satisfaction.

The Moderating Impact of Motivation on the Relationship among the Positive Impact of Attitude against Sustainable Tourism

Much research has concluded that three basics about costs and benefits impact the community, which include the economic and tourism aspects (Hsieh et al., 2017; Nunkoo & So, 2016). According to Santos-Roldán et al. (2020), the principle of sustainability also involves a balance among these three dimensions: environmental, economic, and social (Liu et al., 2015). Some studies have shown a good relationship with sustainable tourism establishments (Hsieh et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2015). In the research context about motivation, the urgency of value is associated with the intention of returning to a place

based on word of mouth when looking for destinations (Santos-Roldán et al., 2020). This is the reason tourists are increasingly showing a commitment to sustainability and a higher interdimensional balance of motivation for this type of tourism. Instead, there is a direct and positive relationship among the variables that has been observed by others, while the study focuses on the straight relationship among the positive impacts, and motivation within implications for tourism sustainability (model hypotheses 4 and 7). However, moderation may influence the positive impact of motivation and also sustainable tourism. Therefore, the formulation of the hypothesis is as follows:

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Motivation has an impact at moderate to positive and also attitudes against sustainable tourism.

The moderating effect of motivation in the relationship between experiential satisfaction and attitude toward sustainable tourism

A higher level fosters good behavior in the future like revisits to the destination (Castillo Canalejo & Jimber del Río, 2018). The relationship between attitudes and motivation against sustainable development has been observed in previous research (Huang & Liu, 2017; H.-C. Wu et al., 2016). The high level of satisfaction of visitors can reflect positive attitudes in the future, for example, the intention to visit again. As stated in the scientific literature, there is also an important correlation between attitudes and motivation as well as satisfaction with tourism on an ongoing basis. However, there is a conflict between moderation and the impact of motivation which has not been studied further while the correlation between attitude and satisfaction with its impact on tourism has been continuously observed. The conclusion is that there is an increasingly high motivation to make repeat visits to the ecological environment, which influences the impact of the relationship and is also getting bigger. The hypothesis is thus:

Hypothesis 5 (H5): There is a moderating impact of motivation between attitudes and satisfaction with sustainable tourism.

The moderating impact of motivation in the relationship between destination image and attitude against sustainable tourism.

A positive destination image can be enhanced through distribution channel members, for example, good performance can be optimized through the distribution to operators specializing in destinations (Day et al., 2012). The website can also provide information regarding the destination so that it can provide different accessibility for visitors with accurate information and specific images (Tigre Moura et al., 2015). The positive performance of a destination can be optimized by tapping wholesale and also distributing travel agents where a website can provide important information about the convenience for visitors to get an accurate visualization of the destination and description before they go on holiday (Kong et al., 2015). Several researchers have provided quantities related to the effectiveness of improving performance and also achieving targets that need to be implemented. From a creativity perspective, the final installer needs to make changes to the performance that is to be induced because changes related to the organic image cannot be done just like that. In addition, changes in advertising through newspapers,

such as reports and articles, in which reviews on this destination include several categories, such as risk literature, safety descriptions, and risks that individuals accept regarding the destination as they have studied it before they travel and also their perceptions, could have an impact on the condition of the destination in the future (Chew & Jahari, 2014). The hypothesis is that:

Hypothesis 6 (H6): There is a moderating impact related to the destination's performance and the attitudes of tourism enthusiasts on an ongoing basis.

Correlation related to attitudes and motivation for continued tourism

This study of motivation, which is used as an internal factor, can integrate and guide individual attitudes where psychological indicators show the direction so that they can behave in a certain method so that their goals and actions can be satisfying to visit a destination where motivation is very closely related to intentions and attitudes (Santos-Roldán et al., 2020). When tourists decide on a destination, the experience gained can determine good commitment (L.-L. Chang et al., 2014).

Profiles or details of the identity of customers can continuously involve tourists in choosing a commitment to the environment because the motivation of tourists can have a positive impact on visitors' intentions (Huang & Liu, 2017). The experiences that are interesting to them can influence their perceptions so that a direct relationship between motivation and attitude can be developed. The following hypothesis is formulated:

Hypothesis 7 (H7): Motivation has a direct and positive influence on attitudes toward sustainable tourism.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative research was used to conduct this research. Questionnaires were distributed online to Bandar Lampung University students who had visited Pahawang Island.

The research design serves as an explanatory study that aims to test the theory and whether it makes it stronger even rejects the theories or hypothesis (Agustin & Sari, 2023). This research was also supported by a qualitative approach to deepen quantitative data while making it easier to understand the data and information obtained in the field (Kasaeng, 2023).

Population and Sampling

The population in this study included students of the Faculty of Economics and Business of the University of Bandar Lampung. The sampling techniques used nonprobability sampling with purposive samplings. To meet the objectives of the research, a digital event questionnaire was created with an orientation to enable continuous exploration of tourism development and also the behavior of residents. A waste collection technique is a purposive sampling technique that uses the perceptions of informants to respond to questions asked. The informants were determined by experience and their role in the tourism industry about existing policies and were deliberately determined to create a broader perspective. Various informal informants were known to the researcher personally, both metal and close friends, so that they could be achieved.

The study used a specific criterion with some respondents of as many as 200 students. Tourist perception, positive impact, experiential satisfaction, destination image, motivation, and sustainable development attitude were the six variables of the study.

Measurement

Concerning the use of the instrument, there was a translation of the scale that was specifically submitted to the population in terms of lingual characteristics, and all variables were reviewed through the number 1, which only means strongly disagree, and also 5, which means strongly agree, where each item in this case is adapted from previous research. Positive or sociocultural, environmental, and economic impact items were adapted through previous research by Pai et al. (2020) and H.-C. Wu et al. (2016).

Items that have a relationship to the religion of the destination are shown through previous relationships. There is various evidence of the relationship between behavior in sustainable tourism development, and also the concept of motivation has been adapted by previous research.

Data Analysis

The correlation of each variable that has a moderating impact was examined through a Partial Least Squares or PLS equation model. There are also suggestions confirmed by previous research and the software applied is Smart PLS 3.0. The implementation of a single instrument collects data and signals the urgency of examining the existence where the process and design for administering questionnaires are followed by classifying

different measures. The general impact of the responses is examined through previous research, and exploratory indicators record 12 factors that include 17% of the total. Thus, there are no indicators for the questionnaire that do not include other items until there is validation of the model for multiple levels, including when validity has been carried out.

Table 1: Variable Measurement

Variable	Item	Description
Introduction	P1	Have you ever visited Pahawang Island
Tourist Perception (Purwanto & Yudistira, 2021)	TP1	Protection of marine ecosystems
	TP2	Cleanliness of the destination environment
	TP3	Waste management
Positive Impact (Pavlič et al., 2017)	PI1	Tourism encourages the awareness of natural resource protection
	PI2	Tourism encourages the awareness of natural resource protection
	PI3	Tourism augmented the local recreational resource and places
Experiential Satisfaction (Pai et al., 2020; H.-C. Wu et al., 2016)	ES1	It is worth visiting a sustainable city
	ES2	Contribute to environment protection and Sustainable Tourism
	ES3	I can accomplish the purpose of this travel.
Destination Image (Kanwel et al., 2019)	DI1	The place description must be near by the motive to visit opinions.
	DI2	A favorite place higher the satisfaction from tourist.
	DI3	As maintained by the most crucial antecedent by the purchase and also the post-purchase by the tourism behavior
Motivation (Meimand et al., 2017; Mohaidin et al., 2017)	M1	Travel somewhere that offers an ecological environment
	M2	Experience different cultures from mine
	M3	It is done to contacting with people abroad
Sustainable Tourism Development Attitude (Obradović & Stojanović, 2022; Su et al., 2017)	STDA1	Behavioral and also attitudes satisfaction and don't make the residents disturbed
	STDA2	Tourism needs to be developed in harmony with natural and cultural environment
	STDA3	The diversity of nature must be valued and protected

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Description

Based on the data obtained from 200 respondents, the characteristics based on gender, age, and the semester being spent are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Data Criteria of Respondents

Characteristics	Description	Percentage
Gender	Male	35%
	Female	65%
Age	17 Years	2%
	18–21 Years	52%
	21–25 Years	51.5%

Current Semester	1 st Semester	5.5%
	3 rd Semester	23.5%
	5 th Semester	30%
	7 th Semester	41%

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

Outer Model

Analysis testing of the measurement implementation related to the model was conducted to review the details between variables in Latin as well as correlation to reliability as well as discriminant and convergent validity.

Convergent Validity

This is a measurement in the form of a model to review the relationship between constructs and item scores in which reliability is determined if the value exceeds 0.70, but in the scale development phase, there are loadings in the range of 0.5 to 0.6 which can still be accepted. Thus, the results for this outer prove that there is a value below 0.6 as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Outer Model

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

SmartPLS output for loading factor gives results in the following table:

Table 3: Outer Loading

	TP	PI	ES	DI	M	STDA
TP1	0.909					
TP2	0.756					
TP3	0.846					
PI1		0.858				
PI2		0.899				
PI3		0.804				
ES1			0.722			
ES2			0.706			
ES3			0.795			
DI1				0.804		
DI2				0.839		
DI3				0.845		
M1					0.756	
M2					0.850	
M3					0.862	
STDA1						0.870
STDA2						0.919
STDA3						0.868

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

In the diagrams and tables, the indicators must be more than 0.70 or they are valid for the structure.

Discriminant Validity

Table 4 shows the discriminant impact of the validity test that implements cross loading values as a factor maintained to find the validity when there are bigger variables compared to the main problem

Table 4: Cross Loading

	TP	PI	ES	DI	M	STDA
TP1	0.909	0.603	0.557	0.542	0.435	0.561
TP2	0.756	0.513	0.489	0.622	0.572	0.489
TP3	0.846	0.592	0.487	0.477	0.403	0.524
PI1	0.616	0.858	0.497	0.560	0.514	0.618
PI2	0.609	0.899	0.466	0.542	0.483	0.604
PI3	0.512	0.804	0.444	0.521	0.417	0.514
ES1	0.471	0.541	0.722	0.486	0.387	0.370
ES2	0.358	0.293	0.706	0.384	0.316	0.325
ES3	0.510	0.378	0.795	0.584	0.517	0.460
DI1	0.531	0.507	0.589	0.839	0.592	0.515
DI2	0.586	0.589	0.568	0.845	0.551	0.610
DI3	0.509	0.477	0.501	0.804	0.553	0.530
M1	0.379	0.406	0.435	0.514	0.756	0.520
M2	0.478	0.472	0.465	0.575	0.850	0.532
M3	0.521	0.487	0.489	0.592	0.862	0.671
STDA1	0.519	0.583	0.451	0.616	0.650	0.870
STDA2	0.556	0.601	0.483	0.598	0.643	0.919
STDA3	0.599	0.628	0.470	0.552	0.568	0.868

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

Various factors with certain cross-loading values are complicated by other variables. Therefore, the conclusion is that conceptual and latent variables have improved to the point that family roots can be shown by AVE (Average Variance Extracted) and these values for each consumption have a difference that is above 0.5, so there are no problems with another testing model.

Composite Reliability and Cronbach’s Alpha

Reviewing based on reliability when it is known, while alpha cages carry out metal measurements and also variable reliability so that the value can exceed 0.6.

Table 5: Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach’s Alphau	Composite Reliabilityyu	AVE
Tourist Perception	0.786	0.876	0.704
Positive Impact	0.816	0.890	0.731
Experiential Satisfaction	0.599	0.786	0.551
Destination Image	0.773	0.869	0.688
Motivation	0.763	0.864	0.679
Sustainable Tourism Development Attitude	0.863	0.917	0.786

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

This proves that the AVE on every variable has a construction of more than 0.50, which means all constructions are trusted. This maintained that every variable has a big discriminant validation. The result shows every variable finds the composite release and then it is found that the whole variable has a big realism level. Table 5 indicates that Cronbach’s alpha for all variables shows construction values > 0.70. Thus, the results indicate that most of the variables of the study have met the criteria of the value of Cronbach’s alpha. Therefore, every variable has a high rate, and we can conclude that indicators implemented here have mostly a high discriminatory validity.

Analysis of Internal Models

An internal model evaluation is taken out to check the accuracy:

Determination Coefficient (R²)

There are three categories of grouping of R Square values, including R square value 0.67 that is included in the strong category, R Square value 0.33 that is included in the moderate/medium category, and R Square value 0.19 that is included in the weak category. It is taken out to ensure the structural model. As mentioned previously, the data mechanism implements the SmartPLS 3.0 program when the R square value is maintained.

Table 6: R Square Results

	R-Square
Motivation (Z)	0.502
Sustainable Tourism Development Attitude (Y)	0.493

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

There are 50.2%, which means that the variables of tourist perception, positive impact, experiential satisfaction, and destination image influence motivation by 50.2%. The remaining 49.8% is also affected by the others, while the value of R square sustainable development is 0.493. Therefore, it indicates 49.3%. This means that the variables of tourist perception, positive impact, experiential satisfaction, destination image, and motivation influence the sustainable tourism development attitude by 49.3% and the remaining 50.7% is influenced by other variables.

Table 7: Fit Model

	Saturated Modelu	Estimated Modelu
SRMR	0.075	0.133
d_ ULS	0.964	3.032
d_ G	0.453	0.579
Chi-Square	522.667	592.542
NFI	0.749	0.715

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

The results of this test show evidence related to NFI (Normed Fit Index), which also means FIT, so the conclusion is that there is a high GoF, and it is suitable for implementation in carrying out the test.

Hypotheses Testing

There is also an evaluation between the correlation of various consequential and the hypothesis this time is expressed through p-values and statistical tests that exceed 1.96 as well as p-values less than 0.5 the result is shown in Table 8.

Tabel 8: Path Coefficients (Direct Influence)

	Direct Effect	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	t-statistics (O/STDEV)	p-values	Sig.
H1	TP → PI	0.680	0.683	0.055	12.261	0.000	Sig
H2	TP → ES	0.611	0.614	0.049	12.558	0.000	Sig
H3	TP → DI	0.654	0.658	0.059	11.073	0.000	Sig
H7	M→STDA	0.702	0.703	0.056	12.612	0.000	Sig

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

This proved that they had t-statistics values more than 1.96 and p-values with less than 0.05.

Table 9: Path Coefficients (Indirect Influence)

	Indirect Effect	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	t-statistics (O/STDEV)	p-values	Sig.
H4	PI→M→STDA	0.172	0.174	0.077	2.221	0.027	Sig
H5	ES→M→STDA	0.156	0.163	0.078	2.010	0.045	Sig
H6	DI→M→STDA	0.468	0.460	0.087	5.398	0.000	Sig

Source: SmartPLS Output (2024)

The hypotheses are accepted because the t-statistics value is > 1.96 and p-value is < 0.05

DISCUSSION

Tourist perception has a significant influence on positive impact. The results of the study show that the t-statistic value on this variable is 12.261 and the p-value is 0.000, which means that the variable of tourist perceptions directly affects positive impacts. Studies in environmental psychology literature suggest that our attachment to environmental settings has a profound positive impact on our physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being (Ramkisson, 2023). Psychological environmental studies can be viewed through a large positive impact on both physical and mental emotions, and some results show the views of tourists will have a positive impact so that what they feel can bring sympathy or sympathy from the community can improve culture and its values (Joo et al., 2019).

Tourist perception has a significant influence on experiential satisfaction. The results here prove the t-statistic value on this variable is 12.558 and the p-value is 0.000, which means that the tourist perceptions variable directly affects experiential satisfaction. This study is consistent with research by Kotler et al. (2017), which noted that in a competitive tourism business, experience satisfaction is considered the primary separator and is increasingly the key element of a business strategy. The results are supported by previous research conducted by Kasaeng (2023). Students at the University of Bandar Lampung believe that the views of tourists have a positive influence on visiting tourist places influenced by the satisfaction of the experience after they visit the tourist place.

Tourist perception has a significant influence on the destination image. The results here prove the t-statistic value is 11.073 and the p-value is 0.000, which means that the tourist perceptions variable directly affects the destination picture. The results of this study are supported by previous research carried out by (Ceylan et al., 2021; Haarhoff, 2018; Matlovičová & Kolesárová, 2012). A good destination description may be augmented by the channel distribution, like inbound operators, travel agents, and wholesalers who specialize in destinations (Day et al., 2012).

A website can provide destination information that makes it easier for tourists to visualize the destination and get a more accurate picture of the place before traveling (Tigre Moura et al., 2015). The positive performance of a destination can be optimized by tapping wholesale and also distributing to travel agents where a website can provide important information about the convenience for visitors to get an accurate visualization of the destination and description before they go on holiday.

Motivation has a significant influence on sustainable tourism development attitude. The results show that the t-statistic value is 12.612 and the p-value is 0.000, which means that the motivation variable directly affects the sustainable tourism development attitude. This is contrary to the previous research that has been done by Santos-Roldán et al. (2020).

However, research by Meimand et al. (2017) found that motivation has a significant influence on sustainable development attitudes. Motivation is defined as a theoretical explanation of how it has been implemented in various studies related to behavior as a form of representation of the background of people's actions and needs.

Motivation also has other meanings from an individual to behave or express the causes when he or she repeats an action according to the theory of socialization (Elliot et al., 2006). Socialization states the characteristics of the association that will develop tourism to review funds and the effectiveness of its development. Meanwhile, indicators related to intrinsic motivation are a form of indicator to determine other support for the SDGs (Kayat, 2002).

Motivation to moderation has a positive impact on sustainable tourism development attitudes. The research results show that the t-statistic value for this variable is 2.221 and the p-value is 0.027, which means that the motivation variable has a positive impact on sustainable tourism development attitude.

Motivation is one of human behaviors' core views, and there are a variety of fundamental principles that are built into the perception of human motivation (Jiang et al., 2019). Motivation related to tourism that has been developed sustainably when determining a destination and also the experience gained is crucial to making motivation more satisfied and optimizing the loyalty of tourists when the profile or identity details of consumers include tourists who have a full commitment to sustainable environmental awareness (Kim et al., 2017).

Motivation moderation in the influence of experiential satisfaction on sustainable tourism development attitude. The research results show that the t-statistic value for this variable is 2.010 and the p-value is 0.045, which means that the motivation variable moderates experiential satisfaction toward sustainable tourism development attitude. This research is following research conducted by Liu et al. (2016). Students at Bandar Lampung University believe that if tourists feel the novelty of the destination, they can increase satisfaction and also emotional excitement and return to be the evaluation material to make the satisfaction higher.

Motivation moderation in the influence of destination image on sustainable tourism development attitude. The research results show that the t-statistic value for this variable is 5.398 and the p-value is 0.000, which means that the motivation variable moderating on destination image toward sustainable tourism development attitude (Baloglu & McCleary, 1999) is the whole indicator.

Motivation relates to the intention to decide if (L.-L. Chang et al., 2014) the experience obtained at that place is important to satisfying and increasing tourism loyalty. The sustainable tourism customer profile involves tourists who care for the whole environment and care about sustainability because of the motivation that they give when they visit the place and contribute to local activities.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

According to the results of the research and analysis, variables such as tourist perception, positive impact, experiential satisfaction), destination image, and motivation have a positive and significant influence on sustainable tourism development attitude because they have a p-value of less than 0.05 or can be inferred that all hypotheses are accepted. In more depth, this study expands understanding by detailing how motivation as an indirect intervention variable has a fairly high impact on the sustainable tourism development attitude in sustainable tourism in the future.

The research also contributes to the development of knowledge about how tourists can preserve natural resources and contribute to developing future tourism, especially from the perception of tourists from different countries. Thus, the research provides valuable contributions in filling the knowledge gap about how real tourists' attitudes toward preserving and contributing to environmental sustainability to develop the tourism of the future. When it finished reviewing the reports and studies based on the content, it would be confirmed that a protocol is needed.

Suggestions

Nature tourism in Lampung Province is the focus of this research. By investigating various types of tourism in various regions of Indonesia, future research is expected to make a greater contribution to the progress of national tourism. As a result, future researchers need to analyze and make measurements that can be applied in a variety of contexts.

This research only examines motivation as a moderating variable. Future research is expected to determine whether the relationships found in this study also apply to other moderating variables. However, the focus of this research is sustainable tourism. This relevance will increase with these new circumstances. Therefore, it will be very easy to repeat this work in the future when national mobility is fully permitted and the entry of foreign tourists is allowed. The authors argue that this aspect may change due to increased tourist sensitivity. In short, methods to improve the tourism sector are needed. Sustainable tourism development can help tourists feel more comfortable and enjoy time with more people. It would also be interesting to conduct a study that examines what tourists do to find out the impact on their attitudes toward sustainable tourism development, especially in Indonesia.

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Tabulation of Respondent Data

Item	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Value	%	Value	%	Value	%	Value	%	Value	%
TP1	37	18,5%	126	63%	15	7,5%	22	11%	0	0%
TP2	57	28,5%	129	64,5%	7	3,5%	5	2,5%	2	1%
TP3	54	27%	104	52%	14	7%	28	14%	0	0%
PI1	62	31%	100	50%	19	9,5%	17	8,5%	2	1%
PI2	61	30,5%	100	50%	18	9%	20	10%	1	0,5%
PI3	63	31,5%	101	50,5%	20	10%	14	7%	2	1%
ES1	66	33%	118	59%	12	6%	4	2%	0	0%
ES2	67	33,5%	120	60%	10	5%	2	1%	1	0,5%
ES3	60	30%	120	60%	13	6,5%	6	3%	1	0,5%
DI1	50	25%	120	60%	21	10,5%	9	4,5%	0	0%
DI2	60	30%	111	55,5%	16	8%	13	6,5%	0	0%
DI3	49	24,5%	124	62%	14	7%	11	5,5%	2	1%
M1	57	28,5%	126	63%	13	6,5%	4	2%	0	0%
M2	49	24,5%	119	59,5%	24	12%	7	3,5%	1	0,5%
M3	43	21,5%	123	61,5%	22	11%	11	5,5%	1	0,5%
STDA1	61	30,5%	106	53%	18	9%	15	7,5%	0	0%
STDA2	47	23,5%	117	58,5%	20	10%	16	8%	0	0%
STDA3	54	27%	114	57%	11	5,5%	18	9%	3	1,5%
Total		100,00%		100,00%		100,00%		100,00%		100,00%